

CELLULOSE NANOCOMPOSITES – CONTROLLING DISPERSION AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES THROUGH NANOCELLULOSE SURFACE MODIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

The use of cellulosic nanofibers as reinforcement in polymer composites offers great advantages over their petroleum counterparts. Apart from being strong, stiff and low density; they are obtained from naturally occurring resources and as such are favorable from an environmental point of view. A major problem while studying nanomaterials is their tendency to agglomerate, thus leading to inhomogeneous distribution within the polymer matrix. This often results in stress concentrations in the matrix rich regions when the material is subjected to load and therefore, limits the potential application of these materials. A common approach to circumvent this is by surface modification, which facilitates the dispersion in non-polar matrices. An environmental friendly approach, inspired by clay chemistry, was used to functionalize the CNC surface. It was shown that the CNC could be modified in a rather convenient way to attach a variety of functional groups on the surface. Primarily, the problem of cellulose nanocrystal (CNC) distribution in a hydrophobic polymer matrix is investigated. Composites prepared from modified CNC were studied and compared with unmodified CNC. The distribution of the CNC is carefully monitored at different stages via UV-Vis spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The mechanical properties of the resulting materials were characterized by dynamic mechanical as well as uniaxial tensile tests. It was shown that a homogeneous distribution of the CNC exposes a tremendous amount of surface area to interact with the matrix. In such a case, the stress transfer is much more efficient and perhaps, the matrix behavior is modified, which leads to significant improvements in the mechanical properties.

Keywords: Cellulose Nanocomposites, Mechanical Performance, Surface modification

1. INTRODUCTION

Wood based pulp fibers have traditionally been used in paper and related applications. However, cellulosic materials have also been studied as reinforcement for polymer matrices. The most notable of these have been plant fibers and wood based fibers with a diameter of approximately 30 μm and lengths up to a few mm. During the past decade, several new and energy efficient methods have been developed to isolate the nano-scale building blocks from these natural fibers. The cellulose nanofibrils (CNF) or cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) obtained by these processes are 4-20 nm in diameter and a few μm in length. These nanoparticles are extremely interesting as reinforcement, owing to their exceptional intrinsic properties – modulus around 100 GPa and strength of up to 1 GPa [1-4]. This combined with their low relative density (1.5) makes them a viable alternative for conventional petroleum based fibers. The recent awareness regarding environmental concerns has given a further impetus to move towards more ‘green’ alternatives. Materials obtained from non-food based resources are a good option. Cellulose is primarily found in wood, annual plants, in some animals (tunicates) and also produced by bacteria.

The chemical structure of cellulose nanoparticles (CNC and CNF) consist of several thousand glucose units linked together by glycosidic bonds. The crystal structure (of wood cellulose) is generally believed to be square in cross section, consisting of 36 cellulose chains arranged in parallel. Due to the chemical structure having a large number of hydroxyl groups, cellulose nanoparticles are characterized by a strongly hydrophilic behavior, which makes it convenient to disperse them in water. On the flip side, these nanoparticles tend to agglomerate when they are in hydrophobic polymeric matrices due to the incompatible high energy interface. Surface modification of the cellulose nanoparticles is one way to circumvent this.

The aim of surface modification of nanocellulose is to introduce stable electrostatic charge and obtain better colloidal dispersions or to tune its hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity and control compatibility with various solvents and polymer matrices [5, 6]. In general, surface modification of cellulose can be divided into three groups (1) native surface chemistry of nanocellulose resulting from the extraction process (for example sulfate esters groups originating from sulfuric acid hydrolysis). This primarily depends on the processing method adopted to isolate the nanoparticles (2) physical adsorption of surfactants or polyelectrolytes on the surface of nanocellulose and (3) covalent modification (for example esterification, etherification, silylation and polymer grafting). In this approach, the reactivity of the surface hydroxyl is utilized to modify them [2]. Several reports have explored various options [7-16].

In this work, surface modification of CNC was carried out using an environment friendly approach, where a quaternary ammonium salt was absorbed on the CNC surface. Thereafter, composites of the modified and unmodified CNC with Polyvinyl Acetate (PVAc) were prepared and characterized. Cellulose nanocomposites as a reinforcement for PVAc matrix have been studied earlier. In this work, the main focus was to study the effect of dispersion on the properties of the final composites.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

Materials

High purity softwood pulp was kindly supplied by Domsjö Fabriker AB. Polyvinyl acetate with $M_w = 83\,000$ was bought from Aldrich). All other standard chemicals were obtained commercially and used without any modifications.

Preparation and modification of cellulose nanocrystals

Cellulose nanocrystals were prepared from wood pulp using sulfuric acid hydrolysis according to method described by Beck-Candanedo [17] with minor modifications. In summary, dried wood pulp (20 g) was added to 175 ml of 64 wt% sulfuric acid (preheated to 45°C). The reaction was continued for 60 min and then was stopped by diluting to 10% of the original concentration. The acid from the suspension was removed by centrifuging/redispersing in water and thereafter by dialysis over several days. The resulting suspension of cellulose nanocrystals was sonicated and the agglomerates were removed by centrifugation. The concentration of the obtained suspension, as determined by gravimetric analysis, was 1.1 wt%. The surface charge was determined by conductometric titration, and was 0.5 mmol/g. The surface of the CNC was modified with quaternary ammonium salts according to a procedure previously developed in our laboratory, with minor modifications [18].

Preparation of CNC/PVAc nanocomposite

Composites with 1, 3, 5, 10 and 20 wt% of modified CNC as well as unmodified CNC were prepared. The desired amount of CNC was dispersed in 10 ml of toluene by sonication for 30 s at 30 % maximum power. PVAc was then added and the total weight of the nanocomposite was kept as 1 g. The suspensions were stirred overnight to ensure complete dissolution of PVAc and then cast in an aluminum petri dish and dried at room temperature for 3 days and further at 60 °C for 2 days.

Characterization of CNC/PVAc nanocomposites

The mechanical properties of the films were tested using Instron 5944 instrument equipped with a 500N load cell. The samples were cut into rectangular strips, 5 mm wide and 0.2 mm thick. The gauge length was 30 mm and the strain rate was 50 %/min. The samples were conditioned at 23°C and 50 % relative humidity for 2 days prior to testing. Strain in the initial elastic region (up to 0.2%) was measured using 2D Differential Speckle Photography (DSP). Correlation was done using the LIMESS software.

Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) was done using a TA instrument Q800 in tensile mode on rectangular samples (4 mm by 10 mm). Measurements were taken at a frequency of 1Hz and an amplitude of 10 μ m. The temperature scan was performed between – 20 °C and 120 °C at a rate of 5 °C/min. The glass transition temperature was determined from the loss modulus peak.

The morphology and the degree of dispersion of unmodified and C12 modified CNC in PVAc matrix was studied using Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM, Hitachi S-4800, Hitachi, Japan). The cross section of the samples was prepared by fracture under liquid nitrogen. The samples were attached on a split mount stub using carbon tape and coated with a thin layer of Pt/Pd (Cressington 208 sputter coater).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Surface modification using adsorption of quaternary ammonium salts offers a wide range of functionalities, which can be introduced onto cellulose (see Figure 1) [18]. In this work, CNC prepared by sulfuric acid hydrolysis were modified by dodecyltrimethylammonium chloride (having 12 carbon chains in the backbone). The reaction between quaternary amine and CNC was confirmed by FT-IR.

More detailed study was performed using cellulose nanocrystals having carboxylic groups (CNC-C) and stearyltrimethylammonium chloride, quaternary amine with the longest hydrocarbon chain (C18). It was shown, that CNC-C modified with C18 can be redispersed in organic solvent, and individualized rod-like particles were observed. To investigate the effect of washing step and the length of the alkyl chain, model surfaces were prepared by spin coating of the CNC-C suspension on Si wafer and contact angle measurement was used to quantify hydrophobicity. The contact angle increases from 12° in the native state to 48° when modified with dodecyltrimethylammonium chloride, and further increase to 71° after washing with toluene. It is believed that during the washing steps, the micelles of quaternary amine can reorganize themselves and all unbound amine is removed. However, it was found that model surface modified with C8 (octyltrimethylammonium chloride) has a contact angle with water of 74° and C12 (dodecyltrimethylammonium chloride) resulted in a contact angle as high as 85° . Therefore for further experiments, C12 was used as it gave the highest contact angle of the selected quaternary amines.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the reaction of quaternary amines with carboxylic acid on CNC surface. The different ammonium salts represent the potential functionalities that can be attached to the CNC surface. In this work, however, the starting CNC had sulphate groups on the surface, instead of carboxylic. (The figure is reproduced from Ref. 18 with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry)

Suspensions of cellulose nanocrystals having carboxylic groups have a gel-like consistency at solid content higher than 0.5 wt% (due to the high surface charge density) and therefore the adsorption needed to be performed on very diluted suspensions (less than 0.1 wt%), leading to the need for removal of large volumes of water during freeze drying and thus consuming high amount of energy. Cellulose nanocrystals prepared by sulfuric acid hydrolysis have lower surface charge and their suspensions flow even at higher solid content (few wt%), enabling the adsorption to be performed at more concentrated suspensions and therefore reducing the energy consumption of the process.

Composites with Polyvinyl Acetate (PVAc) as the matrix were prepared by solvent casting. Since one aim of the study was to study the effect of dispersion on the material properties, the CNC dispersion was characterized at each stage. It was observed that the colloidal stability of the modified CNC dispersion in toluene was much higher as compared to the unmodified CNC. Consequently, the optical transparency of films was affected. While the composite films with 10 wt% unmodified films were hazy white, transparent films with modified CNC upto 20 wt% of modified CNC could be obtained. Uniaxial tensile tests of the composites showed that the strength of composites with unmodified CNC increased as compared to the neat PVAc, but the increase was substantially lower as compared to the reinforcement with modified CNC. Furthermore, it was also observed that the optimum composition of the modified CNC composites was 3 wt%. Higher loading of modified CNC led to decrease in the ultimate strength of the composites. On the contrary, the optimum loading with modified CNC composite was observed to be 10 wt%. This is partially due to the incompatible interface between the unmodified CNC and PVAc and also due to heterogeneous distribution of unmodified CNC in PVAc matrix. Presence of agglomerated CNC substantially limits the mechanical performance of the composites. The agglomerates are evident from SEM images of the cross section (Figure 2).

Figure 2 presents the freeze fractured cross section images of the composites. PVAc has a smooth cross section as seen in figure 2a. Figure 2b shows the cross section of the composites with 5 wt% unmodified CNC. The CNC particles appear to be agglomerated which is apparent as two clearly distinct regions at the micron scale – smooth regions of PVAc, and regions with rough morphology containing bundles of CNC. On the other hand, composites with unmodified CNC had a much more homogeneous cross section and the CNC appears to be well dispersed, even in composites with 10% modified CNC (Figure 2c, 2d).

Figure 2. Freeze fracture SEM images of cross section of (a) pure PVAc film (b) composite film of PVAc with 5 wt% unmodified CNC, (c) composite film of PVAc with 5 wt% modified CNC and (d) composite film of PVAc with 10 wt% modified CNC film.

4. CONCLUSION

Composite films of PVAc with unmodified and modified CNC were prepared by solvent casting. It was observed that the surface modification of the CNC had a significant impact on the colloidal stability of the CNC particles in toluene. Subsequent addition of the polymer to this suspension and film formation by casting led to transparent films with modified CNC as opposed to hazy, translucent films with unmodified CNC. The uniform distribution of the modified CNC particles was also verified from cross section images of the composite. This had a positive effect on the mechanical performance of the composites – the strength of the modified CNC composite films were ca. 4-5 folds higher as compared to the same loading of unmodified CNC.

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